

July 28

Take any n where $n \in \mathbb{Z} : n \geq 1$
 if n is even $\left\{ \frac{n}{2} \right\}$
 if n is odd $\left\{ \frac{n+1}{2} \right\}$

$\rightarrow$ Noz
 $\downarrow$ Noz

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	...
0	0	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	
2	1	6	11	16	21	26	31	36	41	46	51	56	
4	2	7	12	17	22	27	32	37	42	47	52	57	
6	3	8	13	18	23	28	33	38	43	48	53	58	
8	4	9	14	19	24	29	34	39	44	49	54	59	
...													
1	0	34	64	94	124	154	184	214	244	274	304	334	
3	10	40	70	100	130	160	190	220	250	280	310	340	
5	16	46	76	106	136	166	196	226	256	286	316	346	
7	22	52	82	112	142	172	202	232	262	292	322	352	
9	28	58	88	118	148	178	208	238	268	298	328	358	
...													

(odd group)

	0	1	2										
	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	$(n \cdot 3 + 1)$
Noz	0	1	1	2	2	3	4	4	5	5	6	7	...
Noz	4	0	6	2	8	4	0	6	2	8	4	0	...
													...

(even group)

	0	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26	28	$\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)$
Noz	0										1	1	1	1	1	...
Noz	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	...

Ipost group flow